

Rice cultivars with disease resistance

V. Mariappan and P. Durairaj, Coimbatore, India

Four hundred and ninety-one rice cultivars were screened under natural field infection during kharif 1980 for resistance to the following rice diseases: brown spot at 12 locations, bacterial blight at 15, and tungro at 5.

The cultivars in the table were found resistant or moderately resistant to those diseases at Coimbatore as well as in other locations. ■

Cultivars found resistant at Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Disease	Designation	Cross	Disease severity grade at Coimbatore ^a (0-7 scale)
Brown spot	IET7137	MTU15/Waikoku	1
	IET7145	T141/Baok//T141	1
	IET6753	Hema/RPW6-13	3
	IET7134	Shirauni/Goenchiew	3
	IET7117	Ratna/TKM6	
	IET6880	RP31-49-2/LMN	3
Bacterial blight	IET6361	IR24/TKM6	3
	ET5953	CR161-42-16 (Vijaya/W12708)	3
Tungro	IET6268	CR63-5218-1/Pankaj	3

^a1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant.

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at CRRI, India

A. Anjaneyulu, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack 753006, Orissa, India

The life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens* collected and reared locally were tested on seedlings of 10 rice varieties in the CRRI greenhouse, Cuttack, India, 22 November to 14 December 1978. To study the insect's life span 400 adult insects — 20 females and 20 males for each variety — were given an acquisition access time of 2 days on tungro-diseased plants. The insects survived 1 to 22 days on 1-week-old seedlings. Their life span averaged 8.5 days — 8.9 days for female insects and 8.0 days for the male.

On the basis of average insect life span, Ptb 18, IR34, and Gam Pai 30-12-15 were more resistant than the other varieties in the test (see table).

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at CRRI, India, 1978.

Variety	Life span (days)		Infective insects (%)	Retention (days)		Infected seedlings		
	Long-est	Av ^a		Long-est	Av	%	No./insect	No./infective insect
Ambemohar 159	21	11.9 a	44	1	1.0	11	0.44	1.00
TN1	18	11.6 a	81	4	1.8	34	1.44	1.77
Pankhari 203	22	11.6 a	25	3	1.4	8	0.31	1.25
IR26	19	10.1 ab	84	3	1.6	34	1.38	1.63
Habiganj DW8	22	9.9 ab	0	0	0	0	0	0
Latisail	21	8.9 b	69	5	2.0	31	1.41	2.05
Kataribhog	22	8.8 b	6	1	1.0	1	0.06	1.00
Gam Pai 30-12-15	13	4.8 c	50	3	1.7	23	0.81	1.63
IR34	14	4.7 c	59	3	1.8	28	1.08	1.74
Ptb 18	5	2.6 d	9	1	1.0	3	0.09	1.00
Max or av	22	8.5	43	5	1.3	17	0.70	1.31

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

The tungro transmission differed remarkably among the varieties. About 18% of 1,251 seedlings inoculated by 320 viruliferous insects became infected. But the insects were unable to transmit the tungro virus to Habiganj DW8 and were

poor in transmitting it to Kataribhog, Ptb 18, and Pankhari 203 (see table). Those varieties were probably more resistant to tungro than the other six in the test. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Rice yield losses due to gall midge infestation in northern Thailand

Weerawooth Katanyukul, Sawang Kadkao, and Somnuk Boonkerd, Entomology and Zoology Division, Agriculture Department, Bangkok, Thailand

The rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* has been an endemic pest of rice in northern

Thailand for half a century. Although insecticides and resistant varieties have proved effective for gall midge control, they are not adopted widely by farmers.

An experiment was conducted in a farmer's field at Ban Parauk, Cheingrai Province, to determine if gall midge damage would reduce the rice yield and

whether insecticide control was economically feasible.

Four rice varieties were studied: RD 1 (susceptible), Leaug-Laung (local), and Dok-Ma-Li 105 and Niew-San-Pa-Tong (recommended traditional). The experiment used a split plot and was replicated three times. The main plot was